

Note on *Otiorhynchus phasma* Rottenberg, 1872, with a new synonymy (Coleoptera, Curculionidae)

Abstract

The recently published catalogue of Palaearctic Curculionoidea (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA et al. 2017) lists for the genus *Otiorhynchus* Germar, 1822 *O. (Podonebistus) phasma* Rottenberg, 1872 and *O. (Metopiorrhynchus) garibaldinus* Solari & Solari, 1909, both distributed in Sicily and in Calabria (SPARACIO 1999, OSELLA et al. 2004, ABBAZZI & MAGGINI 2009).

The taxonomic history of *O. phasma* and of *O. garibaldinus* is quite complex. *Otiorhynchus phasma*, a quite isolated species, was described from Mount Etna (ROTTENBERG 1872: 226). In the same paper ROTTENBERG named *O. heteromorphus* Rottenberg, 1872 another unusually shaped *Otiorhynchus* again from Mount Etna (Nicolosi) whose description is just slightly different from that of *O. phasma*. Most of the subsequent authors failed to recognize the above mentioned species (BERTOLINI 1872, WEISE 1883, VITALE 1890 & 1900, RAGUSA 1904a, 1904b), whereas STIERLIN (1883), probably having seen type(s) of it, placed *O. phasma* in the genus *Trogloorhynchus* SCHMIDT, 1854, leaving *O. heteromorphus* inside *Otiorhynchus*. This arrangement was followed by WEISE (1891), VITALE (1900), and RAGUSA (1904a, 1904b). WEISE (1906: 600) was the first who established the synonymy between *O. phasma* and *O. heteromorphus*, most likely after the study of types. He listed it under *Otiorhynchus* subgenus *Dorymerus* Seidlitz, 1890. However, LUIGIONI (1929: 870) and PORTA (1932: 57) still kept the species under *Trogloorhynchus*. On the contrary, WINKLER (1932: 1431), again considering *O. phasma* an *Otiorhynchus*, did not place it in any of the subgenera described by REITTER (1912, 1914), followed by LONA (1936: 223). Afterwards, *O. phasma* was placed by MAGNANO & ALONSO-ZARAZAGA (2013: 335) into the subgenus *Podonebistus* Reitter, 1912, probably due to its very elongate shape which makes it look similar to some species from the Balkans, Eastern Europe, Caucasus and Central Asia, although there might not exist a closer relationship between them.

Instead, *O. garibaldinus* was listed by PORTA (1932), ABBAZZI & MAGGINI (2009), MAGNANO & ALONSO-ZARAZAGA (2013), and ALONSO-ZARAZAGA et al. (2017) under the subgenus *Metopiorrhynchus* Reitter, 1912, according to the placement firstly proposed by LUIGIONI (1929: 863).

We had the opportunity of studying the female type of *O. garibaldinus* (Fig. 1) together with a series of specimens of *O. phasma* identified by the late specialist Luigi Magnano who studied types of both species, and who did not find any differences between them. Thus, we establish here the synonymy: *Otiorhynchus (Podonebistus) phasma* Rottenberg, 1872 [= *O. garibaldinus* Solari & Solari, 1909; **syn. n.**]. This same synonymy is contained in an unpublished note by Magnano read by both authors of this paper in which is also stated that *O. phasma* is a parthenogenetic species, since thus far no males of it are known.

Keywords: Curculionidae,
Otiorhynchus phasma,
synonymy

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Fig. 1: *Otiorynchus phasma* Rottenberg: on left side female type of *O. garibaldinus* Solari & Solari, size mm 5.7; on right side female specimen of *O. phasma* from Sicily: Messina, Nebrodi, Monte Soro, m 1800, 8.VI.2007, Baviera & Bellò leg., size mm 5.4, to the same scale. Photo by Francesco Sacco.

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